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MANAGING CHANGE AND QUALITY COSTS IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Conditions of political and economic instability, competition in domestic and foreign markets, and globalisation of the world economy are prompting manufacturers of industrial products to pay particular attention to improving product quality and safety [4]. Understanding the essence of quality as a product property that satisfies all consumer requirements plays a key role in changing attitudes towards methods and resources for ensuring the expected product quality. [6]. The decision to implement the concept of sustainable development in Ukraine [1] has created additional challenges for industrial enterprises, as the dissemination of risk assessment methodologies in parallel with the standardisation of environmental, food, and economic security, occupational safety, compliance, information, and energy security, and energy efficiency has been done. The destabilisation of Ukraine's economy, characterised by outdated equipment and technologies, combined with a growing trend of increasing shortages of both skilled and unskilled labour, has created conditions for the

convergence of international management standards and advanced technologies in production and management processes at industrial enterprises. William E. Deming's statement, "It is not necessary to change. Survival is not mandatory" [3] is very relevant in the current reality of our country, and only a deep understanding of the economic and social consequences of leaving everything unchanged is a prerequisite for improvement.

Fig. 1. Change management scheme through quality cost management (compiled by the author based on [2])

The desire of Ukrainian industrial manufacturers to adopt modern standards and methods, based on the best practices of global leaders in industrial production, presents challenges and contradictions that impact business processes, production processes,

and economic benefits. First of all, there is a logical question of assessing the economic component of this complex process. It should be noted that the psychological factor in implementing such improvements, which is expressed in the readiness of the enterprise's management and all employees for change, plays a key role [5]. At the strategic level of enterprise management, including planning, assessment and forecasting of economic benefits that a manufacturer can obtain at all stages of these changes, we propose to implement this through quality cost management (Fig. 1).

Quality cost management, as a key tool for economic planning and evaluation of all processes at the strategic level of industrial enterprise management during periods of change, enables effective and efficient product quality management to achieve planned results and benefits.

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